

*Will the Elder Brother Enter the Feast?
The Significance of Jesus's Pause at Luke 16:1
Between the Prodigal Son and the Canny Steward.*

Part of a longer analysis into the pauses in speech in the Bible

See *A Study in Silence*

ABSTRACT

Following the Pharisees' criticism that Jesus welcomed sinners, the Parable of the Prodigal Son (Luke 15:11–32) exposes their lack of mercy through the figure of the elder brother. The Parable of the Canny Steward (Luke 16:1–13) extends the challenge by exposing their attachment to wealth. Through shared vocabulary, parallel crises, similar strategies for securing a future and a common emphasis on divine generosity, the two parables form a unified appeal. The pause invites reflection, while the steward's urgency demands an urgent response.

Luke 16:1

Ἔλεγεν δὲ καὶ πρὸς τοὺς μαθητάς ἄνθρωπός τις ἦν πλούσιος ὃς εἶχεν οἰκονόμον καὶ οὗτος διεβλήθη αὐτῷ ὡς διασκορπιζὼν τὰ ὑπάρχοντα αὐτοῦ

This pause is between two parables—the Prodigal Son (15:11–32) and the Canny Steward (16:1–13) for it is connected by: Ἔλεγεν δὲ καὶ πρὸς τοὺς μαθητάς, “Then he went on to say *also* to the disciples”. We will come to reasons beyond the obvious for the pause after we have investigated the links between the parables.

“The Pharisees and the scribes kept muttering, saying: ‘This man welcomes sinners and eats with them’” (15:2). This prompted the parable of the lost sheep and the lost coin (verses 4–10), which both conclude with the lesson, “Joy arises among the angels of God over one sinner that repents”, and the parable of the Prodigal Son. All three parables were addressed to the Pharisees and the scribes in an endeavour to provoke their sense of joy in the recovery of something lost (verse 3). Presumably the disciples were present to listen. However, with the first parable of chapter 16, Jesus καὶ, “also” addresses his disciples.

So, in what way do the parables answer the accusation and in what way are the two parables connected?

The two parables share a network of verbal, thematic and theological links.

Although ἀσώτως is word that gives the young son the title Prodigal, it is the word διασκορπίζω that links the two parables. The young son “*squandered* his property”; the steward is accused of handling his master’s goods “*wastefully*”. Both have recklessly dispersed other’s resources. διασκορπίζω is only used nine times in Scripture, so these two occasions would seem to form a literary connection: both figures stand exposed as failed managers of what ultimately belonged to another—the son asked for his inheritance before his father had died, so there is a sense that the son was a steward of his father’s estate. The steward had authority over his master’s accounts. The disciple of Christ is a steward of God’s gifts and will be held responsible for their use.

Both stories pivot on an inner turning point—a moment of reckoning. The pivot in the first is when the Prodigal comes to his senses (15:17); in the second when the steward is told he is going to lose his job he asks himself, “What am I to do, seeing that my master will take the stewardship away from me?” (16:4). In each case, a crisis produced a moment of reflection, a moment to think strategically about survival.

The result was that they both decided decisively to act quickly to secure their future: the Prodigal decided to return to his father and rehearsed his plea; the steward decided not to be a manual labourer or a beggar, but to reduce the debts of his master to gain favour with his creditors.

The Prodigal hoped that his strategy would ensure that he would be received by his father (15:18, 19); the steward hoped that his strategy would ensure that he would be received into the homes of the creditors (16:4). This anticipated one of Jesus’s lessons: “make friends... so that when it fails, they may receive YOU into the everlasting dwelling places” (16:9).

Given the gravity of the offences, both parables contain a surprising positive response: the father extravagantly welcomed the prodigal; the master commended the steward’s shrewdness. In both cases, the response overturned normal expectations of strict justice. The obvious “sinner” (prodigal/dishonest steward) acts wisely while the expected “righteous” (elder brother/Pharisees) are exposed for wrong attitude.

Both parables revolve around material resources: the Prodigal wasted wealth selfishly while the steward used wealth to build relationships. Jesus wants us to use our resources for eternal purposes (16:9–11). The Prodigal’s experience answered the Pharisees and scribes rebuke about entertaining sinners; the steward’s experience answered the Pharisees’s love and misuse of money (16:14). It was an exposure of the Pharisees in two stages: the first parable exposed their lack of mercy (elder brother); the second exposed their love of money.

Central to both stories is the father and the master. The son knew that his father was generous and merciful—this was the mainstay of his plan. The steward knew that his master was generous and merciful—this was the mainstay of his plan. In fact, the master could see that the actions of the steward were actually a compliment of the master’s reputation.

The lessons from the son and the father story are implicit, but the lessons from the steward story were made explicit by Jesus (16:8–13). Those lessons Jesus drew at the end of the parable of the canny steward seem to apply to both parables.

We are all faced with a crisis. Our life is short, the sand is slipping away beneath our feet. In addition, the Kingdom is coming; the separating of the sheep and the goats may be imminent. We don’t know which will come first—death or the Kingdom. Being imperfect, we are unrighteous, so we need to run to our heavenly Father for mercy. We could also be accused of handling our resources—our time, our energies, our money—wastefully in relation to Jehovah’s* priorities. How will we respond? How will we secure our eternal ‘employment’?

Money is not an important thing in Jesus’s estimation, it is a thing of least concern. However, how we use this thing of least concern can, like the steward, shows where our priorities are. We are encouraged to use our money to establish vital friendships and eternal employment (16:9, 10).

If we use our money for selfish purposes, why would Jehovah entrust us with other things? The use of this money demonstrates our focus in life (16:11).

Our money is actually not ours but God’s. He has endowed us with skills, abilities and opportunities to earn it. To act as if our money is entirely the result of our own efforts is a delusion. Once we have come to our senses we can now prove to Jehovah that we will use our resources from now on to maintain our friendship

* See Appendix, page 6.

with him. In that way we 'prove faithful in connection with what belongs to another, and we gain everlasting life for ourselves'.

Why might Jesus have paused?

As mentioned above, there is an adjustment of audience. Before the pause, the focus was on the Pharisees and scribes; after, the disciples were addressed directly, but the Pharisees are still present and listening as 16:14 shows. The pause created a layered effect allowing Jesus to give an urgent message to his disciples while still appealing to the Pharisees to have a change of heart.

Also, there is an unresolved appeal at the end of the first parable: the father was pleading with his older son to drop his sanctimonious attitude and share the joy that a sinner had repented and returned (15:31, 32). The older son represented the Pharisees and scribes, and they were being addressed. Jesus wanted them to have a moment to reflect, to see the parallels and change their attitude, to have their resistance dissolved by the beauty of their heavenly Father's love. Will the older brother enter the party? And while they were pondering over this, the parable of the canny steward showed them they did not have much time to think about it.

Bible quotations are from the *New World Translation of the Holy Scriptures, with References*, 1984, unless otherwise indicated.

The Introduction to this edition of NW contains this explanation:

Where “YOU” is printed in small capital letters, it shows that the pronoun is plural. Also, where the plural number of a verb is not apparent, its plurality is indicated by printing it in small capital letters. If the context already clearly indicates plurality, then no special capitalization is used.

APPENDIX

In the Bible the divine name יהוה occurs almost seven thousand times, more often than any of God's titles, and more often than any other separate Hebrew word.

There are many theophoric names in the Bible. The majority of Bible translators transliterate those names which have the first two syllables of the divine name as Jeho. Hence: Jehonathan, Jehoshua, Jehoshaphat, Jehoahaz, Jehonadab, Jehoram etc. When the Israelites shortened a name they would not abbreviate but they contracted it by removing syllables from the middle of the name. So Jehonathan was reduced to Jonathan; Jehoshua became Joshua; Jehonadab became Jonadab. God's name was contracted to Jah, hence: Elijah, Abijah and Hallelujah etc. Therefore, the divine name must have had three syllables, not two.

We believe that a י is more likely to be transliterated as a y in English, and a ו is more likely to be transliterated as a w. So the divine name could be *Yehowah*. However, most Bible scholars avoid any transliteration. They use the tetragrammaton in Hebrew letters יהוה, or they display the divine name as YHWH. This is all well and good, but it is inconsistent with their transliteration of other Bible names. If they are to be consistent then they should either use Yehonathan for Jonathan or show the Hebrew letters יהנתן, or YWNTN. Sometimes they use *Yahweh* which disregards how names were shortened, and it only has two syllables.

The argument that the vowels of יהוה are those of אֱלֹהֵינוּ does not hold up because the vowels are not the same.

Gesenius pointed out that "Those who consider that יהוה was the actual pronunciation [of God's name] are not altogether without ground on which to defend their opinion. In this way can the abbreviated syllables יהו and יו, with which many proper names begin, be more satisfactorily explained."

We believe that *Jehovah* is a reasonable transliteration of the tetragrammaton.